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The incomplete recovery of Danish coastal waters following reduced nutrient inputs and oligotrophication

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Danish coastal waters were severely affected by eutrophication in the 1980s, prompting the implementation of national nutrient reduction plans. The aim of this study was to explore the recovery of Danish coastal waters and report trends for selected indicators of eutrophication. Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP), chlorophyll a, light penetration depth, eelgrass main depth limit, a benthic fauna index (DKI), and bottom water oxygen concentration. We report on the temporal and spatial trends of eutrophication in 109 coastal waterbodies from 1980 to 2023. The analysis revealed that although improvements have been observed in several waterbodies, eutrophication continues to affect large areas. The national eutrophication status improved until the early 2000s, followed by stagnation. This trend was primarily driven by changes in winter DIN and DIP concentrations, whereas oxygen concentrations, eelgrass main depth limits, and DKI remained relatively stable throughout the study period. The means of chlorophyll a and light penetration depth showed signs of recovery until 2012 and 2021, respectively, followed by trend reversals. These findings suggest that reductions in nutrient levels have been pivotal in driving Danish coastal waters towards recovery; however, current mitigation efforts are insufficient to ensure that Danish coastal waters can achieve status as 'not affected by eutrophication'.

KEYWORDS

classification, eutrophication, heat, indicators, integrated assessment, monitoring data, shallow ecosystems

1 Introduction

Eutrophication is a threat to coastal ecosystems worldwide, with large-scale effects on ecosystem functioning, stability, and services (Nixon, 1995; Cloern, 2001; Malone and Newton, 2020). There are multiple derived effects of coastal eutrophication, such as increased frequency and distribution of hypoxia (Diaz and Rosenberg, 2008), changed species community composition (Rosenberg et al., 1987), loss of biodiversity (Cloern, 2001), increased frequencies of harmful algae blooms (Anderson et al., 2002; Ærtebjerg et al., 2003), and loss of biologically engineered habitats (Bell et al., 2014; Krause-Jensen et al., 2021). The

potential economic benefits of reducing nutrient supply have been estimated at Baltic scale (Gren et al., 1997) and more recently at Danish scale (Andersen et al., 2019). The causes of coastal eutrophication have been known for decades (Nixon, 1995; Cloern, 2001), yet eutrophication continues to be a persistent problem for coastal ecosystems worldwide.

Numerous definitions have been proposed for eutrophication owing to the complexities regarding causes, processes, and effects (Nixon, 1995; Andersen et al., 2006). In this study, we draw on the definition ‘the enrichment of water by nutrients, especially nitrogen and/or phosphorus and organic matter, causing an increased growth of algae and higher forms of plant life to produce an unacceptable deviation in structure, function, and stability of organisms present in the water and to the quality of water concerned, compared to reference conditions’ (Andersen et al., 2006). Using this definition, indicators of eutrophication can be divided into causative factors, direct effects and indirect effects (Andersen, 2012).

Causative factors of eutrophication are the enrichment of the aquatic environment by nitrogen (N) and/or phosphorus (P), and organic matter. Nutrient dynamics in the water column are inherently affected by the nutrient input, residence time, currents, hypoxia, seasonality, amongst other factors (Conley et al., 2000). For example, dissolved inorganic nutrients are removed from the water column by phytoplankton during the growing season, but will be recycled upon degradation and remineralisation of these primary producers (Hansen and Høglund, 2024).

Direct effects of eutrophication include increased algal growth (Andersen et al., 2006), as primary production in marine ecosystems is predominantly limited by the availability of nutrients and light (Conley et al., 2000). Therefore, an increase in N or P alters the naturally occurring nutrient ratios in the ecosystem, causing a shift not only in phytoplankton primary production and biomass (Cloern, 2001), but also in community structure (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003). As the nutrient concentration increases and phytoplankton growth is stimulated, light attenuation is enhanced, reducing the amount of light reaching the seabed (HELCOM, 2013).

Indirect effects consist of changes to eelgrass depth limits, benthic invertebrate communities and oxygen concentrations (Riemann et al., 2016; Andersen et al., 2017). Each of these parameters is affected differently by the direct effects described above. Microbial degradation of organic matter and respiration from benthic organisms consume oxygen in bottom waters. Hence, elevated phytoplankton biomass increases oxygen consumption and the risk of hypoxia in bottom waters (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003). Oxygen depletion can cause large-scale changes in invertebrate community composition, biomass, and functioning, as large, slow-growing species are replaced by fast-growing opportunistic species after a period of low oxygen (Carstensen et al., 2020). Longer periods of oxygen depletion can even cause a collapse of the benthic community (Diaz and Rosenberg, 1995; Conley et al., 2007) and in the absence of oxygen, the sediment concentration of the toxic compound hydrogen sulphide increases, potentially eradicating benthic invertebrates (Conley et al., 2009; Vaquer-Sunyer and Duarte, 2010). Furthermore, hypoxia influences the phosphorus and nitrogen cycles in sediments: anaerobic conditions cause release

of iron-bound phosphorus to the water column and reduce immobilisation of N, leading to increased availability of DIN and DIP, further strengthening hypoxia (Cloern, 2001; Conley et al., 2009). As eelgrass growth and distribution are mainly limited by light conditions and physical disturbances (Krause-Jensen et al., 2021), decreased light penetration due to increased phytoplankton biomass restricts benthic macrophytes to shallower depths with sufficient light levels (Nielsen et al., 2002a). Healthy, extensive eelgrass meadows are valuable as they promote biodiversity (Colvin and Snelgrove, 2025), provide coastal protection by dissipating wave energy (Hansen and Reidenbach, 2012), reduce sediment resuspension and improve water clarity (Carr et al., 2010), sequester carbon and take up nutrients (Leiva-Dueñas et al., 2023).

Danish coastal waters receive nutrient inputs from the land, atmosphere, and adjacent seas. The main sources are leakage from agricultural soils and animal husbandry. Discharges from urban areas and industry contribute to a lesser degree following upgraded wastewater treatment (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003). Danish coastal waters exhibited signs of eutrophication with accelerating nutrient inputs from the 1950s, peaking in the 1980s (Kronvang et al., 1993) at levels of 120,000 tonnes N annually (Figure 1). Widespread oxygen depletion in the 1980s caused extensive mortality of the fauna in the Kattegat, prompting management actions to reduce nutrient inputs. The first Action Plan on the Aquatic Environment (APAE) was passed in 1987 by the Danish Parliament with the objective of reducing inputs of N and P by 50% and 80%, respectively (Kronvang et al., 1993). To assess the effectiveness of management actions, The Danish National Aquatic Monitoring and Assessment Programme was established in 1988, expanding upon existing regional monitoring programmes (Carstensen et al., 2006; Riemann et al., 2016). In the 1980s, diffusive sources accounted for the largest part of the total N (TN) input; and their relative importance has increased since then (Figure 1). The first APAE was followed by additional APAEs, European Union directives, and River Basin Management Plans. Whereas APAEs focused on regulating nutrient pollution at the source, River Basin Management Plans adopt a recipient-oriented approach, aiming to achieve good ecological status by assessing nutrient loads to individual water bodies (Supplementary Table S1).

The premise of mitigation measures is that the degradation of a coastal ecosystem is a reversible process once pressure is removed. However, once affected by eutrophication, a coastal ecosystem may be subject to a shift in baseline conditions, complicating the relationship between degradation and recovery pathways (Duarte et al., 2009; Carstensen et al., 2011). For instance, Danish coastal waters experienced a partial recovery from 1980 to 2013 in response to nutrient reductions, but the recovery exhibited time lags and feedback processes (Riemann et al., 2016). Moreover, ecosystems affected by recurring hypoxic events are more susceptible to eutrophication and further hypoxia (Diaz and Rosenberg, 1995; Conley et al., 2009; Steckbauer et al., 2011), even with decreasing nutrient concentrations (Conley et al., 2007). The pathway of recovery from eutrophication may be shifted by other pressures such as overfishing and climate change (Cloern, 2001).

The health of Danish coastal waters has been described using a range of indicators to assess and evaluate the expected recovery

FIGURE 1
Reconstructions of total N input to Danish waters from 1900 to 2022. Updated from Conley et al. (2007).

trends following nutrient mitigation (Rask et al., 1999; Carstensen et al., 2006; Conley et al., 2007; Rasmussen et al., 2015; Riemann et al., 2016; Hansen and Høglund, 2024). Despite providing valuable and detailed insights into trends and responses to eutrophication, this multiple indicator approach can make it difficult to convey the overall health of an ecosystem to decision makers, given the complexities of eutrophication. An integrated assessment reduces all information on various ecosystem components, including their spatial and temporal variability, into a single value (Borja et al., 2014, Borja et al., 2016). Marine eutrophication can be assessed using different indicators as well as aggregation and integration approaches (Borja et al., 2014), and the choice of aggregation method can ultimately result in deviating final integrated assessments (Carstensen et al., 2023), highlighting the need for a uniform approach. The multi-metric tool HEAT (HELCOM Eutrophication Assessment Tool) has been used to assess the eutrophication status in the Baltic Sea (Fleming-Lehtinen et al., 2015; Andersen et al., 2017; Murray et al., 2019), the Black Sea (Lazar et al., 2024), Oslo fjord (Ramon et al., 2025), Danish waters (Andersen et al., 2012, Andersen et al., 2020) and on a European scale (European Environment Agency, 2019). However, this tool has never been applied to assess the eutrophication status of Danish coastal waters at a fine temporal and spatial scale. Assessment of eutrophication at water body level can provide valuable insight on regional differences and to the effectiveness of local initiatives, pointing towards local drivers. There is a strong need for coherent, long-term assessments of the eutrophication status of Danish coastal waters to determine whether the current nutrient mitigation efforts are sufficient. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the spatial and temporal trends for seven selected indicators of eutrophication, and via a holistic approach explore the recovery following nutrient reductions after the first APAE. We explored these trends through an integrated assessment approach using HEAT 3.0 to classify the eutrophication status of coastal water bodies (CWBs), thus presenting the first fine-scale eutrophication assessment of Danish coastal waters.

2 Methods

The indicators used were dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP), chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*), the depth at which light intensity is reduced to 16% of the intensity at the surface (light penetration depth) corresponding to the average light requirements of eelgrass, frequency of hypoxia (oxygen), eelgrass main depth limit (eelgrass), and an index for assessing the benthic fauna, the Danish Quality Index ver. 2 (DKI). With the exceptions of DIN and DIP, Danish authorities use these indicators to assess the ecological status in relation to the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD; European Union, 2001). The indicators were grouped into causative factors, direct, and indirect effects.

2.1 Study area

Danish coastal waters are divided into 109 CWBs (Figure 2) based on physical and chemical factors such as salinity, currents, residence time, and depth (Erichsen et al., 2019). To enable consistent comparisons over time, we used delineations and names (name length adjusted for graphical presentation, see Supplementary Table S2) from the current River Basin Management Plans (2021–2027). Note that in Danish, ‘fjords’ is a general term for estuaries, not to be confused with the definition of a classic fjord with a sill (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003). Danish coastal waters are strongly influenced by the mixing of brackish water outflow from the Baltic Sea, freshwater from land, and saline water inflow from the Skagerrak and the North Sea (Conley et al., 2000; Riemann et al., 2016). Outflowing brackish water from the Baltic Sea (salinity ~ 8), forms a surface layer in the Danish straits and Kattegat to the Skagerrak and the North Sea. Conversely, saline water from the Skagerrak (salinity ~ 34) creates a high-density bottom current that flows towards the Baltic Sea (Conley et al., 2000). The salinity gradients in Danish waters, ranging from 0 to 34, are products of the gradual mixing of these different water masses (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003; Hansen and Høglund, 2024). The mean depth of Danish CWBs vary from 0.1 m (Bredningen) to 63.9 m (Østersøen, Christiansø; Rasmussen and

[Hansen, 2018](#)). Tides are limited, except along the west coast of Jutland, where the tidal range in the Wadden Sea region can be >1 m. In addition, wind conditions have a strong modulating effect on the water transportation and vertical mixing in shallow areas ([Conley et al., 2000](#)). Finally, the average temperature of Danish coastal waters vary seasonally by around 15 °C and has increased by approximately 2 °C in the last 40 years ([Hansen and Høgslund, 2024](#)).

2.2 Data sources

We analysed open access data from the period 1980-2023, downloaded from [odaforalle.au.dk](#) and [miljoedata.dk](#) between August

2024 and April 2025. Eelgrass data were supplied by the Danish Centre for Environment and Energy (DCE) in February 2025. All data originated from the Danish National Aquatic Monitoring and Assessment Programme. Measurements from stations within the 109 CWBs were included in the analysis, with a few exceptions of stations just outside the CWB borders (see section 2.2.3). The sampling frequency of all eutrophication indicators varied during this period ([Supplementary Figure S2](#)). For each indicator, analyses were based on data from the months specified in the Danish implementation of the WFD ([Table 1](#); [Christensen et al., 2024](#); for further details, see sections 2.2.1, 2.2.2, and 2.2.3). TN inputs to Danish coastal waters were compiled as described by [Conley et al. \(2007\)](#) and [Riemann et al. \(2016\)](#).

TABLE 1 Overview of included indicators, seasonal window, and number of observations and stations after filtering the open access data according to the criteria listed in sections 2.2.1–2.2.3.

Indicator	Causative factors		Direct effects		Indirect effects		
	Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN)	Dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP)	Chlorophyll <i>a</i>	Light attenuation	Eelgrass	DKI	Oxygen
Seasonal window	Dec–Feb	Dec–Feb	May–Sep*	Mar–Oct	Jan–Dec	Jan–Dec	July–Oct
No. observations	20,944	20,902	113,115	12,919	6,647	16,785	20,865
No. stations/transects	446	444	416	358	1108	1517	658

*Except for CWBs in the Wadden Sea and along the west coast, where observations from March to September were included.

2.2.1 Causative factors

Causative factors of eutrophication were represented by the indicators surface DIN and DIP (≤ 10 m). DIN includes NO_2^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ , and DIP is equivalent to PO_4^{3-} .

2.2.2 Direct effects

Indicators of direct effects are proxies for phytoplankton biomass and consisted of chl *a* and light attenuation. Chl *a* data from the surface (≤ 10 m) were used. Samples of chl *a* prior to 1985 were discarded, as the method for the extraction of chl *a* changed from acetone to ethanol in 1985 (Riemann et al., 2016).

Light attenuation data contained depth profiles of light intensity as a percentage of surface intensity and a corresponding light attenuation coefficient (K_d), estimated from the linear regression of log-transformed light intensity on depth (Markager and Fossing, 2015). K_d was used to estimate the light penetration depth (see the transformation of K_d in section 2.3). Light profiles were removed if they contained less than 10 samples. Estimated K_d values were included in our analysis if the associated correlation coefficient was within the boundaries of 0.8 – 0.99.

2.2.3 Indirect effects

Indirect effects of eutrophication included eelgrass, oxygen, and DKI. The main eelgrass depth limit is the maximum depth on a transect where eelgrass coverage is at least 10%. Depth limits were flagged as censored where supplementary information from surveys indicated that the depth limit was due to factors other than light e.g. maximum depth of the area, dredging for navigation, or availability of suitable substrate. Main depth limits of ≤ 1.5 m were removed, assuming them to be limited by physical stressors rather than by light (Hansen and Høglund, 2024).

For oxygen, deeper observations (> 5 m) were included, and the minimum oxygen concentration was determined for the 2.5 m above the sediment. Each station was assigned to the Skagerrak and North Sea, estuaries and coastal areas, or Danish Strait open waters based on Hansen and Høglund (2024). Stratification in the water column was determined by calculating density differences between surface and bottom water, using thresholds of $\Delta\sigma_T = 0.5$ for estuaries and coastal areas, and $\Delta\sigma_T = 1.0$ for the Skagerrak and North Sea and Danish Strait open waters (Conley et al., 2007). Bottom oxygen observations under stratified conditions were used.

Soft-bottom samples of benthic invertebrates were included if sampled using Haps, Van Veen, Smørstikke, or Kajak-tube. The samples were aggregated to cover 0.1 m² in accordance with the official method of calculating the DKI (Hansen and Josefson, 2020). The R package “ambiR” (not published) was used to calculate AZTI’s Marine Biotic Index (AMBI) (Borja et al., 2000), Shannon-Weiner Index (Shannon and Weaver, 1963) and DKI (Carstensen et al., 2014) for each aggregated sample. AMBI values with few individuals or taxa (≤ 3) were removed as the robustness of the AMBI index decreases (Borja and Muxika, 2005). DKI requires the salinity of the sampled area. Salinity data were available for 106 CWBs, whilst for Horsens Fjord outer, Kattegat, Læsø, and

Bornholm salinity data from the nearest representative station were used.

2.3 Statistical analysis

A general linear model (GLM) was applied to describe the variation between stations, years, and months (Equation 1a). Linear models require normally distributed data and that variance is homogenous (Quinn and Keough, 2002). Therefore, salinity, oxygen, DKI, and eelgrass were analysed untransformed (Equation 1a), whereas DIN, DIP, chl *a*, and K_d were log-transformed (Equation 1b) prior to the variance analysis (see Hansen and Høglund, 2024).

$$\text{Variable} \sim \text{Station}_i + \text{Year}_j + \text{Month}_k + e_{ijk} \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{Variable} \sim \text{Station}_i \times \text{Year}_j \times \text{Month}_k \times e_{ijk} \quad (1b)$$

↔

$$\log(\text{Variable} + a) \sim \log(\text{Station}_i) + \log(\text{Year}_j) + \log(\text{Month}_k) + e_{ijk}$$

where e_{ijk} is the residual, and a is a small constant employed for variables with zero values.

Soft-bottom fauna and eelgrass transects were typically sampled once per year, thus excluding the effect “Month” from the GLM. Eelgrass transects within a CWB were regarded as random subsamples (i.e. residuals; Hansen and Høglund, 2024), additionally excluding “Station” from the GLM. A censored data regression was employed for CWBs containing more than 10% censored data to avoid underestimation of eelgrass main depth limits (Carstensen, 2010) using the same effect as in the GLM; “Year”. Estimated marginal means (hereafter means) were computed from the GLM using the R package “emmeans” (Lenth, 2024) to account for heterogeneity in the monitoring data. Indicators with lognormal distributions were back transformed to the original scale. All computed means are enclosed in the Supplementary Material (Supplementary Figures S3–S9). A transformation of the K_d means was needed for light attenuation to determine the depth with 16% of the surface light intensity (hereafter, light penetration depth), as means were calculated based on K_d . This was identified for the respective CWBs using Equation 2 (Markager and Fossing, 2015):

$$\text{Depth (16 \%)} = \log(0.16) / -K_d \quad (2)$$

Means could not be computed in instances where sampling in a CWB involved missing observations for certain combinations of stations, years, and months. In a few instances, stations with few samples were removed, whereas for some CWBs (Supplementary Table S3), this problem was solved by excluding the effect “Station” from the GLM. For CWBs situated in the Wadden Sea region and along the west coast of Denmark, the 90th percentiles were calculated for chl *a* data from March to October (Table 1; Supplementary Table S4), as these are part of the Northeast Atlantic Geographical Intercalibration Group (Timmermann et al., 2024). Consequently, two methods are applied within the same indicator, reflecting differences in intercalibration approaches

to ensure alignment with national legislation. The estimated frequencies of moderate ($< 4 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ l}^{-1}$) and severe ($< 2 \text{ mg O}_2 \text{ l}^{-1}$) hypoxia were derived (Supplementary Figures S10, S11), drawing on the mean and associated standard errors obtained from the GLM. National means for the indicators were computed annually using a mixed effects model with the R package “lme4” (Zeileis et al., 2015). The fixed effects were “Year”, “Month”, and “CWB”, whereas “Station” was a random effect. The model employed the area of the CWBs ($0.17\text{--}1835.60 \text{ km}^2$) as weights to provide a country-wide representation.

2.3.1 Change point analysis

To identify significant changes in trends and potential change points of the computed annual means on a national scale, a change point analysis was made using the R-package “segmented” (Muggeo et al., 2016). For each of the selected indicators, four models were fitted to the national annual means:

- Model 1: Basic linear model assuming a linear relationship between the means and years.
- Model 2: Basic weighted linear model, assuming a linear relationship between the means and years, using the reciprocal of variances associated with the means as weights.
- Model 3: Piecewise linear regression with one assumed change point. This model allowed the slope of the trend to change at a single timepoint and was as model 2 weighted by the reciprocal of the variances associated with the means.
- Model 4: Piecewise linear regression with two assumed change points. This model was differentiated from model 3 by adding the possibility of another change point.

For each indicator, the four models were compared using the likelihood ratio test from the R-package “lmtest” (Zeileis and Hothorn, 2002) where higher values of log-likelihood indicate a higher explanatory power of the model and where models are significantly different from each other if $p < 0.05$. The simplest model was selected unless a more complex model was significantly better.

2.4 HEAT ver. 3.0

HEAT ver. 3.0 (Ramon et al., 2025) was used to make an integrated assessment by annually classifying each CWB into one of five eutrophication status classes: ‘Bad’, ‘Poor’, ‘Moderate’, ‘Good’, and ‘High’. The stepwise approach in HEAT 3.0 includes:

- a) Identifying eutrophication targets.

Eutrophication targets were identified for each indicator and CWB to classify the eutrophication status at the indicator level. The eutrophication targets specify the values of the boundaries ‘Poor’/‘Bad’, ‘Moderate’/‘Poor’, ‘Good’/‘Moderate’, and ‘High’/‘Good’, thereby establishing the five status classes. Eutrophication targets for the indicators chl *a*, light penetration depth, eelgrass, oxygen, and DKI originated from national legislation (<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2023/792>), as they provide the basis for Danish authorities to assess the ecological status under the WFD (European Union, 2001). Eutrophication targets for the

‘Good’/‘Moderate’ border for DIN and DIP were defined by Christensen et al. (2024). A full overview of the decisions made in setting eutrophication targets, and a list of their values for all indicators, are enclosed in Supplementary Tables S4–S10.

- b) Transformation of indicator value to a standardised eutrophication quality ratio.

The computed mean values for each indicator were standardised using their eutrophication targets with a piecewise linear transformation, according to Carstensen et al. (2023). A eutrophication quality ratio (EQR) was produced, ranging from 0 (worst state for an indicator) to 1 (representing no disturbance from anthropogenic factors). The borders between each of the five status classes have an equal interval of 0.2 on the EQR scale. EQRs were computed by linear interpolation between eutrophication targets and fitting the mean of an indicator (for additional information, see Carstensen et al., 2023). All EQRs for the individual indicators are shown in Supplementary Figures S12–S18. For the indicator oxygen, the EQR was calculated based on the frequency of severe and moderate hypoxia, where the lowest EQR was chosen $\text{CWB}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$. EQR values above 0.6 indicate areas ‘not affected by eutrophication’ whereas EQR values below 0.6 indicate areas ‘affected by eutrophication’.

- c) Uncertainty assessment of indicator values.

Indicator uncertainties were quantified using Monte Carlo simulations, as proposed by Carstensen et al. (2023). Monte Carlo simulations were based on the means and variance estimates (see Section 2.3). The same transformations used in estimating means were also applied when generating simulated values, such that lognormally distributed indicators i.e. DIN, DIP, chl *a*, and light attenuation (K_d), were computed using means and variances on a log-transformed scale. A bias correction was applied to the simulations, ensuring that the mean of the simulations was equal to the original indicator value. Thereafter, the simulations were converted to the original scale for the lognormally distributed indicators and then transformed into EQR (Carstensen et al., 2023). The 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated from these results $\text{CWB}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$.

- d) Integrated assessment.

A hierarchical aggregation scheme was used to aggregate EQR values, ultimately applying the one-out-all-out principle (Figure 3; see Carstensen et al., 2023 for further details). First, the mean of annual EQR values of indicators within the same category was calculated to compute category-specific EQR values and assigned a corresponding eutrophication status class. Second, each category-specific EQR was aggregated into the final integrated eutrophication status using the one-out-all-out principle. Integrated EQRs based on a single indicator were excluded, since the overall assessment relies on multiple indicators.

3 Results

National trends for the seven indicators of eutrophication are presented to explore the underlying processes of eutrophication in Danish coastal waters, together with aggregated assessments, including the final EQR (Figure 3).

3.1 National means of nutrients

The national means of DIN and DIP concentrations declined since the 1980s (Figure 4). The trend of DIN levels can be divided into two distinct periods marked by a change point in 2006 (Figure 4a). The DIN levels displayed a greater decrease prior to the change point ($-10.51 \mu\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 1.86$), followed by a stagnation in the trend ($-1.83 \mu\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 2.91$).

DIP levels increased at the beginning of the study period ($8.24 \mu\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 3.96$), reaching a peak in 1982 ($45.57 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$, CI 32.28 – $64.26 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), although the mean concentration was associated with a large CI (Figure 4b). The peak coincided with a change point,

followed by a decrease ($-1.64 \mu\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 0.23$) until another change point in 1996 marked a stagnation of DIP levels for the rest of the study period ($-0.11 \mu\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 0.066$).

3.2 National means of phytoplankton and light penetration depth

The national mean chl *a* concentration decreased from 1985 ($-0.092 \mu\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 0.012$) until 2012, when a change point marked a trend reversal ($0.079 \mu\text{g l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 0.045$; Figure 5a), which also coincided with the lowest mean chl *a* in the period ($2.52 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$, CI 2.24 - $2.82 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$). In 2023, the mean chl *a* concentration

FIGURE 5

(a) National annual means of (a) chlorophyll a (chl a) concentration (May–September) in the upper water column (≤ 10 m), and (b) 16% light penetration depth (March–October). Red dashed line shows the results of the change point analysis. For chl a, model 3 was chosen, showing a change point in 2012, and for 16% light penetration depth, model 4 was chosen, showing change points in 1996 and 2021. Grey line shows five-year moving average, and error bars indicate the 95% confidence interval of the annual means.

was $3.49 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ (CI $3.11 - 3.90 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$) reaching levels similar to those observed in the late 1990s.

The mean light penetration depth increased slightly from 1990 ($0.049 \text{ m year}^{-1} \pm 0.036$) until the change point in 1996 (Figure 5b). The mean light penetration depth peaked in 1997 ($4.94 \text{ m CI } 3.60 - 4.57$), but the trend stagnated and remained stable for the following approximately 25 years ($-0.0095 \text{ m year}^{-1} \pm 0.0040$). Another change point in 2021 identified a decrease ($-0.24 \text{ m year}^{-1} \pm 0.11$), as the most recent year of the study period marked the lowest mean ($3.10 \text{ m CI } 2.83 - 3.42 \text{ m}$). However, the decrease after 2021 must be regarded with some caution, as a longer period is needed to confirm the robustness of this trend.

3.3 National means of eelgrass, benthic fauna, and oxygen

The national means of the main depth limit for eelgrass decreased from 1984 ($-0.57 \text{ m year}^{-1} \pm 0.12$) until this trend was reversed in 1989 (Figure 6a). Large uncertainty was associated with the first two years due to scarce registrations of the main depth limits of eelgrass. After 1989, the national means of the main depth limit of eelgrass remained stable ($0.018 \text{ m year}^{-1} \pm 0.0049$).

The national means of DKI remained stable ($0.00019 \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 0.00025$), with means ranging from 0.60 (CI $0.53 - 0.68$) in 2003 to 0.73 (CI $0.57 - 0.88$) in 2016 (Figure 6b). No change points were determined for DKI.

The national means of oxygen concentrations were relatively high, ranging from 4.64 mg l^{-1} (CI $3.85 - 5.43 \text{ mg l}^{-1}$) in 1989 to 7.07 mg l^{-1} (CI $6.08 - 8.05 \text{ mg l}^{-1}$) in 1984 (Figure 6c). The mean oxygen concentrations remained stable ($-0.0072 \text{ mg l}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1} \pm 0.0068$). No change points were determined for oxygen.

3.4 National category-specific eutrophication quality ratio

National category-specific EQRs covering the entire study area are presented to investigate the temporal trends (Figures 7a–c).

Category-specific EQRs were calculated at the level of individual CWBs prior to this (Supplementary Figures S19–S21).

The national EQR for causative factors improved during the study period (Figure 7a). From 1980 to the mid-1990s, the national EQR was consistently classified as ‘Bad’ or ‘Poor’, whereas for the remaining years, most EQRs were classified as ‘Moderate’, and even occurrences of years being classified as ‘Good’ in 2006 and 2019.

The national EQR for direct effects improved from the beginning of the study period until 2012 (Figure 7b). The national EQR was classified as ‘Poor’ from 1985 to 1992, improved to ‘Moderate’ from 1993 to 2011, and lastly, peaked in 2012, marking the only occurrence of ‘Good’ status. From 2013 and for the remainder of the study period, the national EQR for direct effects decreased and remained within the ‘Moderate’ status class. This reversal of an increasing trend was only observed for the category direct effects, as well as at the level of individual indicators within the same category (Supplementary Figures S22–S28).

National EQRs for indirect effects were predominantly classified as ‘Moderate’, however, occasionally years were classified as ‘Good’ (Figure 7c). The last recorded ‘Good’ status for indirect effects was in 2009, followed by years classified only as ‘Moderate’. Furthermore, the indirect effects contained the highest proportion of CWBs classified as ‘Good’ or ‘High’ amongst all three categories throughout the years (Supplementary Figure S21).

3.5 National integrated assessment

A general improvement in the national integrated eutrophication status has been observed since the 1980s (Figure 8). Initially, the national eutrophication status was ‘Poor’ but worsened to ‘Bad’ in the period of 1983–1988. From 1989, the eutrophication status class improved to ‘Poor’ and from 2004 onwards fluctuated close to the ‘Poor’/‘Moderate’-border, with most years being ‘Poor’. The national trend has not improved over the last two decades, as illustrated by the five-year moving average. The statuses of the initial three years were accompanied by a high CI and did not include any indicators of direct effects, as chl a and light penetration depth were not included until 1985 and 1990, respectively.

FIGURE 6
 National annual estimated means of (a) eelgrass main depth limits, (b) bottom fauna index DKI, and (c) oxygen concentrations under stratified conditions in July-October. Red dashed lines show results from the change point analysis: (a) model 3 was chosen with a change point in 1989, (b) and (c) model 2 was chosen, showing no change points. Grey line shows five-year moving average. Error bars indicate 95% confidence interval.

3.6 Coastal water body specific eutrophication status

Eutrophication statuses are presented at the level of CWBs to show spatial and temporal trends occurring at higher spatial resolution. The number of potential eutrophication status assessments was $109 \text{ CWB} \times 44 \text{ years} = 4796$ assessments; however, it was

only possible to estimate 2864 integrated assessments (Figure 9). This was the result of the temporal and spatial nature of data sampling being scarcer prior to the establishment of the national monitoring programme in 1988, as well as the inconsistent frequency of sampling in the following period (Supplementary Figure S2). The highest sampling frequencies for DIN, DIP, chl *a*, DKI, and oxygen occurred from the late 1980s to the late 2000s,

followed by a decrease in frequency. Notably, DKI has been sampled very scarcely during the last decade, with frequencies ranging from 6 samples in 2016 to 76 samples in 2015 (Supplementary Figure S2). Conversely, the sampling frequency remained relatively stable for light penetration depth and eelgrass. Sampling efforts have been prioritised higher in some CWBs, enabling a coherent, long-term estimation of the integrated eutrophication status, whilst for others, scarce measurements resulted in a single annual integrated eutrophication status from 1980 to 2023, i.e. Aborg Minde Nor, Als Sund, Bornholm, and Anholt. No eutrophication status could be determined for Horsens Fjord, outer or for Christiansø (Figure 9).

The integrated eutrophication status of the individual CWBs varied widely in time and space (Figure 9), however, predominantly ‘affected by eutrophication’ from the beginning of the study period, followed by a period of improvement. No CWBs were consistently ‘not affected by eutrophication’ (i.e. in ‘Good’ or ‘High’ ES) from 1980–2023 except for Anholt where an integrated status could only be assessed for a single year (2023) with ‘Good’ status. Some areas of concern, such as Limfjorden, have only shown slight improvements in eutrophication status across the study period, with one CWB, Hjarbæk Fjord, exclusively classified as ‘Bad’ or ‘Poor’.

Hjarbæk Fjord, a further 15 CWBs were consistently in ‘Bad’ or ‘Poor’ status. Considering CWBs that have been persistently classified as ‘affected by eutrophication’ (i.e. ‘Moderate’ or lower), the count increases to 46. Note that this estimate excludes CWBs with a single classification of ‘Good’ or ‘High’ status, despite being ‘affected by eutrophication’ for the majority of the study period; incorporating these CWBs adds an additional 21 to this count. In contrast, some CWBs did show improvements, such as Odense Fjord outer, Lindelse Nor, Hevring Bugt, and Kerteminde Fjord. Nonetheless, in recent years, few CWBs were ‘not affected by eutrophication’: in 2023, 13 out of the 93 classified CWBs were in ‘Good’ or ‘High’ status. These are scattered throughout the inner Danish coastal waters. CWBs such as Dybsø Fjord, Avnø Fjord, Nærå Strand, and Bredningen exhibited large fluctuations in eutrophication status during the study period, showing no clear trend. These EQRs were associated with large confidence intervals (Supplementary Figure S29).

4 Discussion

Danish coastal waters were primarily classified in the ‘Bad’ status class from 1980–1990 as illustrated in the national EQR. This period was followed by an improvement lasting until 2004, however, only improving a single status class, i.e. national EQRs primarily classified as ‘Poor’. Following 2004, a stagnation in the improvement was observed as the national EQR fluctuated around the ‘Poor’/‘Moderate’ boundary. Altogether, no single year during the study period could be classified as ‘unaffected by eutrophication’ in regard to the national EQR. This was also the case for several coastal water bodies (CWBs).

4.1 Trends in nutrient concentrations

Eutrophication mitigation efforts in Danish coastal waters were seen as decreasing DIN and DIP concentrations. At the early 1980s, TP inputs were dominated by point sources, and subsequent improvements in sewage treatment under the first Action Plan on the Aquatic Environment (APAE) led to declining DIP concentrations until 1996, when the decreasing trend stagnated. At this time,

all urban sewage treatment plants had been upgraded with tertiary treatment. The succeeding APAEs mainly targeted losses of N from agriculture, as diffuse agricultural sources have dominated TN inputs to Danish waters over the past four decades (Figure 1). These efforts were reflected in the decreasing DIN trend until the change point in 2006.

Nutrient concentrations in open waters are strongly influenced by inputs from adjacent seas; the west coast of Jutland by waters from the German Bight and Kattegat, and the Danish Straits by bottom water from the North Sea as well as surface waters from the Baltic Sea, whilst Danish estuaries are predominantly impacted by local land-based sources (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003). Moreover, local conditions, such as currents, residence time, sediment burial, and denitrification, as well as biological parameters, such as macrophytes and phytoplankton, influence nutrient dynamics (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003; Conley et al., 2009; Carstensen et al., 2020). For instance, distinct soil properties of the catchment area of Limfjorden contributed to a smaller reduction in mean inputs of TN from 1990–2019 compared to the national mean, as the effects of mitigation efforts towards reducing N leaching from agriculture were delayed (Thodsen et al., 2021). This is in contrast to other areas with a more pronounced improvement for the causative factors, such as CWBs in the Belt Sea, the southern Baltic Sea, and Kattegat. This suggests that national mitigation efforts are more effective in some watersheds than in others.

4.2 Trends in chl a and light penetration depth

The national means of chl a generally mirrored decreasing DIN levels until the change point of chl a in 2012, where the trajectory of the two indicators diverged, as the mean chl a concentration increased. Multiple factors affect the chl a concentration in coastal waters, such as grazing pressure (Petersen et al., 2008), light availability, temperature, and nutrient availability (Staehr et al.,

2002). Danish estuaries generally exhibit phosphorus limitation in spring, switching to nitrogen limitation in summer (Conley et al., 2000; Riemann et al., 2016). An increased input of TN during the growing season was found from 2012 to 2022 (Hansen and Høgslund, 2024). Therefore, the observed trend reversal in the mean chl a concentration may reflect elevated TN inputs in the growing season, in combination with an observed increase in temperature of 2 °C during the study period (Hansen and Høgslund, 2024), as increasing temperature can enhance the rate of remineralisation of N and P (Conley et al., 2009). This may be an underlying reason for the observed increased chl a concentration with no concurrent increase in input of nutrients for the same period (2012–2023).

Secchi depth and TN concentrations are strongly correlated in Danish coastal waters (Nielsen et al., 2002b), yet the mean light penetration depth in our study did not show a pronounced response to decreased nutrient loading. Light penetration depth responds rapidly to nutrient enrichment, whereas recovery following nutrient abatement is delayed because of slow removal of excess dissolved organic matter (Hansen and Høgslund, 2024). Therefore, we would expect the initial increase in mean light penetration depth to continue for a longer period following nutrient reductions. However, the light penetration depth peaked in 1996 with no subsequent improvement, indicating that other processes negatively affected the light penetration depth. Processes affecting light attenuation negatively include elevated phytoplankton biomass (Nielsen et al., 2002b), resuspension of sediments, coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM), and particulate organic matter (POM) (Pedersen et al., 2014; Harvey et al., 2019). Since CDOM and POM are not included in the national monitoring programme, monitoring data alone cannot be used to determine the extent to which these factors affect the light penetration depth.

Comparing the eutrophication status for causative factors and direct effects, it was evident that improvements in some areas with regard to causative factors were not similarly reflected in the direct

effects for the same period, e.g. some CWBs in the Belt Sea (Supplementary Figures S19, S20 from Lillebælt, syd to Nyborg Fjord). This suggests that indicators of direct effects are not only affected by DIN and DIP but also by the interplay between the timing of nutrient inputs, increasing temperature, and the light attenuating substances mentioned above. Furthermore, trend reversals in recent years were unique to the indicators of direct effects.

4.3 Trends in eelgrass, bottom fauna, and oxygen concentrations

The national means for the indicators of indirect effects did not show a clear response to decreasing nutrient levels. The mean eelgrass depth limit showed a marked drop until 1989, possibly as a response to high nutrient inputs during the 1980s (Conley et al., 2007), with no or slight improvement for the rest of the period. Signs of recovery of eelgrass depth limits have been reported from 2008 to 2013 (Riemann et al., 2016); however, the present study reveals that the positive trend did not continue past 2013 and does not represent a true recovery, but rather a short-term rebound from an unusually low mean around 2007–2008. This is further supported by the subsequent return of the main depth limits to levels comparable to the early 2000s, indicating no sustained improvement. Additionally, eelgrass meadows are not only pressured by eutrophication, but face multiple stressors, including warming and trawl fishing (Krause-Jensen et al., 2021). Since the 1980s, intensifying pressure from trawling along Danish coasts has coincided with increasing temperatures in surface waters (Krause-Jensen et al., 2003, Krause-Jensen et al., 2021), both of which potentially hinder the recovery of the main eelgrass depth limit. This may be further exacerbated by marine heatwaves (Berger et al., 2024). Furthermore, light is the main limiting factor for eelgrass in Danish coastal waters (Nielsen et al., 2002a); thus, if the decreasing light penetration depth persists beyond 2023, it will likely cause a further reduction in eelgrass depth limits.

DKI can convey responses of the benthic community health to eutrophication (Nielsen and Hansen, 2024), however, the national mean of DKI did not show a pronounced response to decreasing nutrient levels. Stable national oxygen levels may have limited the expected recovery. The lowest mean of DKI was observed in 2003, probably because of the lowest mean oxygen concentration the previous year (Figure 6c). In the late summer of 2002, a severe and extensive hypoxic event occurred in Danish coastal waters (HELCOM, 2003), where benthic invertebrates were partly or entirely eliminated in an estimated area of 3400 km² (Hansen et al., 2003). Furthermore, the benthic fauna diversity and number of species were significantly related to the duration of hypoxia (Conley et al., 2007). Despite the prominent effect of the hypoxic event in 2002 on DKI the following year, this event was not reflected in a long-lasting change in the national means of DKI (Figure 6b). Furthermore, a change in the benthic community composition was observed during the period 1989–2013, with decreasing biomass of filter feeders concurrent with an increasing biomass of deposit feeders (Riemann et al., 2016). Filter feeders may act as a buffer against eutrophication, as they remove large amounts of phytoplankton biomass (Petersen et al., 2008). Therefore, it is

likely that the buffering capacity of the system decreased as less control was applied on phytoplankton, which may be one of the factors underlying the observed increase in chl *a* levels from 2012 to 2023.

Bottom oxygen concentrations are primarily controlled by oxygen consumption and are therefore expected to respond to variations in biological processes and, indirectly, to nutrient concentrations. Moreover, temperature strongly influences bottom water oxygen concentration by modulating the solubility of oxygen in water, controlling the extent of hypoxia by increasing stratification, and affecting metabolic processes (Steckbauer et al., 2011). Therefore, increasing temperatures may have counteracted the effect of decreasing nutrient concentrations on oxygen levels. Furthermore, bottom-water oxygen concentrations are additionally affected by wind speed, as reductions in TN loading were counteracted by decreasing summer wind speed from 1978 to 2003 (Conley et al., 2007; Schourup-Kristensen et al., 2023). Extensive hypoxic events in Danish coastal waters during the 1980s (Conley et al., 2007) could have contributed to shifting baselines, i.e. the ecosystem failing to return to states prior to increasing nutrient loading (Duarte et al., 2009), by changing the benthic invertebrate community and increasing the availability of DIN and DIP (Conley et al., 2007; Høglund et al., 2019). Therefore, a shift in the baseline may explain the relatively stable oxygen concentrations observed. Moreover, a significant increase in the spatial distribution of moderate and severe hypoxic events has been observed for the last 10 years of the study period in inner Danish waters in mid-September (Hansen and Rytter, 2023), thereby rendering larger areas of Danish waters more susceptible to further hypoxia. The lack of recovery for the indirect effects could therefore be due to a variety of interactions, however, most likely caused by the interaction of stable oxygen concentrations from a possible shifting baseline and increasing temperatures.

4.4 Trends in integrated assessment of eutrophication status

Our integrated assessment of the eutrophication status of all 109 CWBs revealed that areas continuously ‘affected by eutrophication’ included Limfjorden, estuaries connected to the North Sea and Skagerrak, estuaries connected to Kattegat, CWBs around Funen in the Belt Sea, and most estuaries connected to the Belt Sea. This emphasises the need to prioritise future management efforts to improve the status of eutrophication in targeted areas. Common for the CWBs continuously ‘affected by eutrophication’ was that nutrients primarily stemmed from their watersheds (Ærtebjerg et al., 2003). Conversely, there was no clear spatial pattern for CWBs that experienced an improvement in eutrophication status, and only few CWBs were no longer ‘affected by eutrophication’ in 2023.

Although Danish coastal waters are diverse and experience large differences in nutrient inputs, the national eutrophication status showed a partial long-term recovery. An ‘oligotrophication’ period (Nixon, 2009) was observed from the late 1980s to approximately 2004. The recovery has not continued past the 2000s, showing that further nutrient reductions are needed to combat eutrophication.

This is supported by the temporal patterns observed following the implementation of the National Action Plans for the Aquatic Environment (APAEs) and River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs). Notably, the implementation of the highly ambitious first and second APAE (1987 and 1998) was followed by an improvement in the national eutrophication status from 'Bad'/ 'Poor' to 'Poor' and from 'Poor' to the border between 'Poor' and 'Moderate', respectively. Conversely, such improvements have not been evident following the implementation of the RBMPs (2014 to present). The spatial trends observed in this study (Video S1) provide valuable insights for national policy makers and are applicable at the finer local scale. Therefore, limited improvements observed during the latter part of the study period are highlighted through our results, indicating where local nutrient management efforts should be prioritised. Overall, these findings offer valuable insights of broader international relevance regarding coastal management, demonstrating that strong political commitment and ambitious mitigation measures maintained over sufficient time scales are essential to effectively combat eutrophication. Conversely, the observed stagnation in the recovery of Danish coastal waters for the previous two decades emphasises the vulnerability of coastal ecosystems to changing political ambitions and continuity. This study emphasised that mitigation of eutrophication on a national scale is further complicated by time lags in the response of biological indicators, suggesting that additional stressors are at play that cannot be mitigated by nutrient reductions alone.

The assessments in the present study were made possible only because of a dataset with wide coverage provided by the Danish national monitoring programme. It is important to stress that assessments of eutrophication in all marine ecosystems depend on robust, frequent, and spatially extensive data (Borja et al., 2016) and highlight the importance of sustained long-term monitoring across a broad selection of stations. Since 2007, the sampling frequency in the Danish national monitoring programme has decreased for most of the indicators included in the present study (Supplementary Figure S2), thereby weakening the foundation upon which this and other integrated assessments are based.

The challenges posed by eutrophication in coastal ecosystems are compounded globally by the pressures associated with climate change, such as warming, prolonged growing season, deoxygenation, and increased runoff, by fishing pressures, input of toxic contaminants, and habitat loss (Cloern, 2001; Henson et al., 2017; Duarte and Krause-Jensen, 2018; Wasmund et al., 2019). These stressors may interact with the effects of eutrophication and counteract current mitigation efforts, further complicating the path to recovery (Cloern, 2001; Duarte et al., 2009). As warming is projected to increase (Bindoff et al., 2019), efforts to reduce nutrient inputs must be reassessed to remain impactful under cumulative effects of multiple stressors. Effects of warming in recent decades may already be a contributor to the observed results, including increasing national chl *a* concentrations and the lack of recovery in oxygen levels despite reductions in nutrient inputs. Future research should support and expand on the findings of the present study by investigating how different scenarios of increasing

temperatures can impact coastal ecosystems, both at the level of individual indicators and via a holistic approach.

5 Conclusion and perspectives

The results presented here suggest that the recovery of Danish coastal waters can be divided into two distinct periods. Following significant nutrient reductions implemented through national nutrient mitigation strategies employed since 1987, 1) a general improvement in the national eutrophication status was observed, as well as signs of recovery for multiple indicators of eutrophication, followed by 2) a stagnation in the improvement and in the responses of multiple indicators, even showing recent trend reversals for chl *a* and light penetration depth. Furthermore, in the face of climate change, efforts to mitigate eutrophication proven impactful in the past may prove inadequate to improve the eutrophication status in the future. Altogether, these findings suggest that mitigation efforts following the implementation of the APAEs were pivotal in driving Danish coastal waters towards recovery; nonetheless, current nutrient mitigation efforts are clearly insufficient with regard to the end goal of Danish coastal waters not being 'affected by eutrophication'. This stresses the need for consistent, long-term mitigation measures and political support to achieve a lasting impact on the eutrophication status, relevant for Danish coastal management and in a broader international context.

Data availability statement

Publicly available datasets were analyzed in this study. This data can be found here: odaforalle.au.dk; miljportalen.dk.

Author contributions

MJ: Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. NM: Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. JA: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. JC: Methodology, Writing – review & editing. LR: Supervision, Writing – review & editing. CM: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Supplementary material

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2026.1785011/full#supplementary-material>

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